

The level of satisfaction of the BSRT students enrolled in the second semester of school year 2020 – 2021 during this pandemic period: An enhancement program

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Abstract

Although a lot of schools now were slowly embracing the modified face-to-face setup, including St. Dominic College of Asia, students and their parents will still be the deciding factor because it is still not yet mandated by the government to require the face-to-face classes. The purpose of this study is to measure the current level of satisfaction of the BS Radiologic Technology students currently enrolled in the second semester of the school year 2020–2021. This study utilized a descriptive, non-experimental, quantitative research design. The researcher invited 26 students through Google Meet and asked a series of questions through a survey questionnaire. Answers should be based on the pointing system (5 = highly satisfied, 4 = satisfied, 3 = neutral, 2 = dissatisfied, and 1 = strongly dissatisfied), while students were asked to explain why they gave such points. The data showed that the BSRT students were neutral towards the registrar, accounting and cashier, Department of Student Affairs and Services (DSAS), and library offices. Most respondents were not able to visit those offices due to the pandemic crisis unless it was urgent or important matters. As for the satisfaction rate of the teaching staff, it was evident that the respondents were satisfied. Although in general different offices and professors received good remarks from the BSRT students, it is recommended to take different proactive customer satisfaction strategies such as offering student feedback surveys, training the department head and staff as well as handling dissatisfied students, giving an incentive to the employees, especially to those who are going the extra mile just to satisfy their clients, and engaging the employees with resources such as training, learning materials, and accounts that will help them in dealing with dissatisfied students.

Keywords: Satisfaction; Radiologic technology; Students; Online classes; Pandemic.

To cite this article:

Araneta, E. R. C. (2021). The level of satisfaction of the BSRT students enrolled in the second semester of school year 2020 – 2021 during this pandemic period: An enhancement program. *SDCA Journal of Radiologic Technology*, 2, 10-14.

Introduction

It is a challenge that all countries are currently attracting to coronavirus disease (COVID-19). This leads to the death of human life, but even under transport, adoption and travel agencies, restaurants, clothing, accessories, products, shopping centers, and even different educational institutions like schools. It also strongly affects various companies, institutions, and universities. Although as of this writing, the Philippine government reduced the alert level to 1, which is closer to the normal living that we used before, there were still restrictions like in education; face-to-face classes are still not mandated or required (Cuaton, 2020; Joaquin et al., 2020; Toquero, 2020). The reason why some students still prefer an online setup is because it is less hassle on their part.

Several authors have stated about student satisfaction through their online courses. Cole et al. (2014) discussed that student-instructor interaction and learner-content interaction were essential in determining how students are satisfied with online learning. While students were satisfied that online learning can be convenient and structured according to the curriculum, issues of timeliness and instructor’s accessibility were less effective than clarity and instructor’s ability in using technology in online courses. Another study from Eom and Ashill (2016) also discovered that although the model had a good predictive ability in determining user satisfaction and learning outcomes, both intrinsic and extrinsic student motivation, including student self-regulation, have no significant relationship with user satisfaction; yet intrinsic student motivation only affected the learning outcomes of the university students. Zainuddin et al. (2019) conducted a flipped classroom approach, wherein students were able to acquire information and continue online learning activities even in their homes. Students were able to observe their learning activities, master the lessons prior to the online discussion, and maintain virtual interaction with peers and instructors.

In local literature, Secreto and Pamulaklakin (2015) used an online student portal where students can maximize their learning experiences within the university. In a study by Burac et al. (2019), online learning tools can help the instructors and students in reinforcing the interface among their lectures. Mallillin et al. (2020) positively revealed that access to online learning platforms helped teachers to improve their professional skills in online learning and teaching through skill, attitude, and knowledge and allowed students to become more flexible and increase their learning dynamics.

Although a lot of schools now were slowly embracing the modified face-to-face setup, including St. Dominic College of Asia, at the end of the day the students and/or their parents will still be the deciding factor because again it is still not yet mandated by the government to require the face-to-face classes. Given that, the purpose of this study is to measure the current level of satisfaction of the BS Radiologic Technology students currently enrolled in the second semester of the school year 2020–2021. Specifically, how do they feel about the services being offered by the registrar, accounting and cashier office, Department of Student Affairs and Services (DSAS), and the library offices? In addition, how do they rate the performances of general education professors and those professors handling professional courses, especially during this online setup?

Methodology

This study utilized a descriptive, non-experimental, quantitative research design. The researcher virtually invited the students through Google Meet and asked a series of questions for a one-on-one virtual consultation. Answers should be based on the pointing system given in Table 1. Evaluation and scoring shows where 5 = strongly satisfied, 4 = satisfied, 3 = neutral, 2 = dissatisfied, and 1 = strongly dissatisfied, in which the quantitative part comes in, plus the fact that it undergoes simple statistical treatment. The students will be asked to explain why they gave such points. Those statements were being recorded and were summarized for further use.

Table 1. Evaluation and scoring

Assigned Points	Numerical Ranges	Verbal Interpretations
5	4.24 – 5.0	Strongly Satisfied
4	3.43 – 4.23	Satisfied
3	2.62 – 3.42	Neutral
2	1.81 – 2.61	Dissatisfied
1	1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Dissatisfied

The questionnaire includes the level of satisfaction from different departments, namely, the Registrar’s Office, the Accounting / Cashier Office, the Department of Student Affairs and Services (DSAS), and the Dominican Learning Resource Center—Higher Education Unit (DLRC-HEU) library. It

also aims to determine the level of satisfaction from the professors of Bachelor of Science in Radiologic Technology based on the following criteria: attitude, attendance, tone and intonation, qualification and competency, mastery of the course and discussion, activities, approachability, and overall rating. Professors from the Bachelor of Science in Radiologic Technology and the General Education Department were rated based on how satisfied students are in their online classes.

Moreover, this study is only exclusive to the enrolled students from first to third-year levels of the second semester of the academic year 2020–2021 of St. Dominic College of Asia, since students from the fourth-year level were already busy in their internship training at the St. Dominic Medical Center. This consultation shows that out of the expected 33 total respondents, only 26 students from first to third-year level participated in the study. The researcher gave an informed consent form to the respondents via Google Forms, where they assured that all answered information is confidential and that they have the right to refuse to participate in research when they feel uncomfortable with the given questions. A frequency and percentage distribution were used to determine if the students from BS Radiologic Technology are satisfied with the assistance of the departments and the professors from different subjects.

Results and Discussion

Table 2. Distribution of respondents

Year Level	Frequency	Percentage
1 st Year	11	42.3%
2 nd Year	8	30.8%
3 rd Year	7	26.9%
Total	26	100%

Table 2 shows the distribution of the respondents who were enrolled in the second semester of the academic year 2020–2021. It was clear that there were 26 total respondents who voluntarily participated in this study. Most of the respondents came from the first-year level, which comprises 42.3% of the overall population, only to be followed by second- and third-year levels with 30.8% and 26.9%, respectively. There were 15 enrolled first-year students, eight (8) enrolled second-year students, and 10 enrolled third-year students. This only means that from first to third-year levels, it is expected that most respondents would come from the first-year level.

Table 3. Satisfaction rate for the different school offices and departments

Indicators	Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Ranking
1. Registrar Office	3.27	Neutral	2
2. Accounting and Cashier Office	3.53	Satisfied	1
3. Department of Student Affairs and Services (DSAS) Office	2.86	Neutral	3
4. College Library (Dominican Learning Resource Center—Higher Education Unit)	2.83	Neutral	4
Average	3.12	Neutral	

Table 3 shows the satisfaction rate of the BSRT students at the different offices at the school. With the accounting and cashier office ranked number 1, having a mean of 3.53, followed by the registrar office with a mean of 3.27, then the Department of Student Affairs and Services (DSAS) office having a mean of 2.86, and lastly from the college library (Dominican Learning Resource Center—Higher Education Unit) that acquired a mean of 2.83. This only meant that BSRT students appreciated the services offered by the accounting and cashier offices because during the one-on-one consultation with them, there were quite a number from them stating that the accounting and cashier offices were responsive, especially during the online enrollment.

Overall, students were in a neutral state when it came to the services offered by different offices such as registrar, DSAS, and the college library (Dominican Learning Resource Center—Higher Education Unit). The offices that are at the bottom two were because most students were not yet familiar with those offices since only the third-year level had the chance to experience those offices during the pre-pandemic period. As for the first- and second-year levels, they were all in online classes, so they were not able to visit those offices.

Table 4. Satisfaction rate for the teaching staff / professors

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Ranking
1. Overall Performance of General Education Professors	3.08	Neutral	6
2. Overall Performance of Professor 1	3.74	Satisfied	3
3. Overall Performance of Professor 2	3.64	Satisfied	4
4. Overall Performance of Professor 3	3.44	Satisfied	5
5. Overall Performance of Professor 4 as Faculty Member	3.95	Satisfied	2
6. Overall Performance of Professor 4 as Program Chair	3.97	Satisfied	1
Average	3.64	Satisfied	

Table 4 shows the satisfaction rate of BSRT students with the teaching staff. It was noticeably visualized that the respondents were satisfied with the overall performance of the fourth professor as program chair, making it ranked first with a weighted mean of 3.97. This is followed by the overall performance of a similar professor as a faculty member with a weighted mean of 3.95. Next is the overall performance of the first professor, having a weighted mean of 3.74, then from the overall performance of the second professor with a weighted mean of 3.64. Succeeding was the overall performance of the newly hired professor for this second semester, who was also the third professor with a weighted mean of 3.44. The last ranking came from the overall performance of general education professors with a weighted mean of 3.08.

On the brighter side, the overall satisfaction rate of our students with the teaching staff was satisfied. Although only the general education professors got a remark that is slightly lower than satisfied, it was because they were still confused in the scheduling of synchronous and asynchronous classes. In addition, students from the first-year level thought that there would be no changes in the arrangement of submitting activities during the first and second semesters, but to their surprise, there were professors now that have a different schedule. As for the professors handling professional courses, which all have received “satisfied” remarks, it is clearly the result of the goals in the BSRT department, which are to balance everything from the technicality side to being humane and friendly. One of the things that the BSRT department were proud of is that the professors are all approachable and have an open line for communication. Zaid and Patwayati (2021) identified that there is a good relationship between customer experience and customer engagement, which also affects customer satisfaction. This can only mean that a customer’s satisfaction level will be greatly affected if they are able to experience something in actual.

Conclusion

The data showed that the BSRT students were neutral when it came to the registrar, accounting and cashier, DSAS, and library offices because most of the respondents were not able to experience those offices, especially for DSAS and the library offices, because of the pandemic, where students are not advised to visit the school unless for urgent or important matters.

As for the satisfaction rate of the teaching staff, it was evident that the respondents were satisfied. Because unlike other offices in which they do not have a consistent interaction if they have a good or bad impression and experience, those offices will be having a hard time bouncing back. Meanwhile, for the teaching staff who were having a weekly interaction with their students, there will be a lot of chances to give a satisfying service, which may affect the satisfaction rate of the students. Since the professors can constantly ask their students if they have learned something or are satisfied with the current discussion and the like, the professors can now plan what actions need to be done to convert that negative feedback from the students into a positive one.

Although different offices and professors received good remarks from the BSRT students, it is recommended to take proactive customer satisfaction steps such as offering student feedback surveys, training the department head and staff as well to handle dissatisfied students, giving an incentive to the employees, especially to those who are doing an extra mile just to satisfy their clients, and arming the employees with resources such as training, learning materials, and accounts that will help them in dealing with dissatisfied students.

References

- Burac, M. A. P., Fernandez, J. M., Cruz, M. M. A., & Cruz, J. D. (2019, March). Assessing the impact of e-learning system of higher education institution's instructors and students. *IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering*, 482, 012009. <https://iopscience.iop.org/article/10.1088/1757-899X/482/1/012009/meta>
- Cole, M. T., Shelley, D. J., & Swartz, L. B. (2014). Online instruction, e-learning, and student satisfaction: A three year study. *International Review of Research in Open and Distributed Learning*, 15(6), 111-131. <https://doi.org/10.19173/irrodl.v15i6.1748>
- Cuatón, G. P. (2020). Philippines higher education institutions in the time of COVID-19 pandemic. *Revista Românească pentru Educație Multidimensională*, 12(1 Sup2), 61-70. <https://www.ceeol.com/search/article-detail?id=859377>
- Eom, S. B., & Ashill, N. (2016). The determinants of students' perceived learning outcomes and satisfaction in university online education: An update. *Decision Sciences Journal of Innovative Education*, 14(2), 185-215. <https://doi.org/10.1111/dsji.12097>
- Joaquin, J. J. B., Biana, H. T., & Dacela, M. A. (2020). The Philippine higher education sector in the time of COVID-19. *Frontiers in Education*, 5, 576371. <https://doi.org/10.3389/educ.2020.576371>
- Mallillin, L. L. D., Mendoza, L. C., Mallillin, J. B., Felix, R. C., & Lipayon, I. C. (2020). Implementation and readiness of online learning pedagogy: a transition to COVID 19 pandemic. *European Journal of Open Education and E-learning Studies*, 5(2), 71-90. <https://oapub.org/edu/index.php/ejoe/article/view/3321/5957>
- Secreto, P. V., & Pamulaklak, R. L. (2015). Learners' satisfaction level with online student portal as a support system in an open and distance elearning environment (ODeL). *Turkish Online Journal of Distance Education*, 16(3), 33-47. <https://doi.org/10.17718/tojde.32741>
- Toquero, C. M. (2020). Emergency remote teaching amid COVID-19: The turning point. *Asian Journal of Distance Education*, 15(1), 185-188. <http://www.asianjde.com/ojs/index.php/AsianJDE/article/view/450/303>
- Zaid, S., & Patwayati, P. (2021). Impact of customer experience and customer engagement on satisfaction and loyalty: A case study in Indonesia. *The Journal of Asian Finance, Economics and Business*, 8(4), 983-992. <https://doi.org/10.13106/jafeb.2021.vol8.no4.0983>
- Zainuddin, Z., Muluk, S., & Keumala, C. M. (2019). How do students become self-directed learners in the EFL flipped-class pedagogy? A study in higher education. *Indonesian Journal of Applied Linguistics*, 8(3), 678-690. <https://doi.org/10.17509/ijal.v8i3.15270>